
The Effectiveness of Functional Training Methods for University Athletes

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Introduction

Functional training is essential for improving athletes' performance by focusing on comprehensive movement coordination. This study aims to assess the impact of functional training on enhancing the speed and overall performance of university athletes.

The relevance of studying the impact of functional training on raising the level of the athlete's speed originates from an athlete's comprehensive movement chain. It also concentrates on harnessing the close coordination of various body parts, particularly when repeatedly doing actions in real competitions. This is particularly important for athletes concerning the efficiency from the start, acceleration and then maintaining speed velocity. Furthermore, there are many forms of training methods that can be adopted by athletes, middle distance and eventually the sprinters stride for various training that aids in preventing injury by supporting the athlete's core stability and preventing muscular imbalances. Therefore, it is important to deal specifically in assuring every opportunity, every advantage no matter how little it contributes in order to have the edge in a competition. It can be stated safely that dealing with the nature of specific training methods has relevance in bringing about more effective training methods that insured athletes excellent performances.

As a player and a teacher that coaches student athletes in the field, it has convinced the researcher that functional training holds favorable and positive implications for enhancing the speed of athletes in training. The training focuses on the series of whole bodily movement and the coordinated neuromuscular functions. Unlike the traditional training methods that focus on enhancing one or several physical qualities, and consequently overlooked harmonious coordination of the body parts of one's athlete's body, could end in a devastating result of physical injuries in sports. These unintended injuries could throw precious time on the planned training modes and schedule and could dampen one's motivation and perhaps lessen their dynamism to proceed training. From this incident it could result to the negative implication for cultivating China's sports talents.

At present with the advancing of technology in every field or industry, functional training methods are incorporated in various training regimes. In recent studies, researches in this endeavor have been directed towards advancing training techniques for optimal

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speed augmentation. Functional training can enhance core stability and support lower limb power that could refine the coordination of body movement at great length.

The objective of this research is to ascertain the relationship between functional training of the athletes in the field. Introducing, discussing, and synthesizing studies and research related to the aforementioned structure form the foundation of this study.

Background of the Study

It was noted that in China, Functional Training gradually gained popularity after the year 2000. It was initially introduced by some pioneering fitness coaches and sports trainers who encountered it in international training courses and later introduced it domestically. With the increasing awareness of health and fitness in recent years and people's exploration of alternative fitness methods, Functional Training rapidly gained popularity in China. Many gyms and training centers began offering Functional Training courses, and numerous coaches received relevant training and certifications. Furthermore, exchanges with foreign fitness brands and organizations accelerated the popularization and development of Functional Training in China. To this day, Functional Training has become an essential part of China's fitness and sports training landscape (Mangona (2023)).

From the late 20th century to the early 21st century, as fitness culture spread in Western countries, Functional Training began to receive widespread attention as a comprehensive and efficient exercise method. Santos (2023) pointed out that functional training initially gained attention in the fields of physical therapy and rehabilitation and gradually gained acceptance in the sports and fitness community.

Functional training, through the simulation of actual competition movements, improves runners' technical skills, body coordination, and explosiveness. Additionally, it effectively reduces the risk of injuries. In summary, Functional training has become a crucial component of modern sprinting training, positively impacting athletes' competitive performance.

Functional Training

It was pointed out in his research that functional training refers to exercise and training that simulates natural movements in people's daily lives, work, or sports. The purpose of this training method is to enhance individuals' physical abilities in real-life situations, improve their functionality, and enhance their movement efficiency according to Joonas (2023). Likewise, Xiao (2023) stated in his research that today, Functional Training is no longer limited to the realm of rehabilitation. It has been widely adopted in sports, fitness, and athletic training to enhance the performance of athletes and the general population, reduce the risk of injuries, and improve the quality of daily life. The core idea is to exercise the body by simulating movements in daily activities, resulting in better functional performance in real-life situations.

Zhang (2023) noted in his study that the origin of functional training can be traced back to the fields of physical therapy and rehabilitation. In the early 20th century, therapists began designing specific recovery exercises for injured soldiers and other patients. The purpose of these exercises was to help them regain basic daily functions such as walking, standing, and lifting. Over time, this function-based recovery approach

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was adopted by sports trainers and fitness coaches and further evolved into modern Functional Training methods.

Saeidi (2023) pointed out that Functional Training has had a profound impact on sports training and has been widely applied in various sports. Functional Training emphasizes simulating actual movements and situations that athletes may encounter in competitions or training, providing athletes with more specific and targeted training. For example, soccer players may engage in a series of exercises that simulate dribbling, shooting, or turning movements to enhance their correlation with corresponding actions in matches.

McDougle (2023) highlighted that traditional isolated muscle exercises often overly emphasize strengthening specific muscle groups, neglecting the overall kinetic chain and stability. Functional training emphasizes the holistic and coordinated nature of the whole body, helping athletes maintain dynamic stability during high-intensity training or competition, thus reducing the risk of injuries.

Alvarenga (2023) pointed out that Functional Training makes athletes' movements more natural and fluid when simulating actions in actual competitions. This not only improves movement efficiency but also makes the actions more economical, prolonging an athlete's performance duration.

Wu (2023) emphasized that Functional Training encompasses not only strength training but also aspects such as flexibility, balance, coordination, speed, and explosiveness, providing athletes with comprehensive skill improvement. Functional Training emphasizes body awareness, requiring athletes to continuously think, perceive, and adjust during training. This enhances the connection between the body and the brain, helping athletes make faster judgments and responses during competitions.

Inoue (2023) highlighted that as the concept of functional training spreads widely, more professional teams and coaches are incorporating it into their daily training routines, not only to enhance athletic performance but also to ensure athletes' physical health and longevity. The comprehensiveness and specificity of this training method have gained wide application and recognition in the field of sports training.

Core Stability Training

Dongaz (2023) stated that Core Stability Training is a new training theory that focuses on strengthening deep muscles and small muscle groups, thereby enhancing body stability. This training method involves creating an unstable surface or support point through equipment, and individuals perform static or dynamic exercises in an unstable state. This helps individuals adapt to unstable surfaces, improve their control over their bodies, and compensate for the lack of training in deep core and small muscles as traditionally addressed in neurophysiology.

Salar Sarvin (2023) pointed out that individuals undergo static support or dynamic movement exercises in an unstable state during Core Stability Training. This helps individuals adapt to unstable surfaces, enhancing their control over their bodies and central control. It also compensates for the traditional neurophysiological training's inadequate focus on the trunk and deep small muscles.

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Sun (2020) explained that by continuously stimulating deep core muscles and the neuromuscular control system through unstable surfaces, core stability training improves both the stability of muscle groups and the enhancement of muscular strength. This leads to increased efficiency in transmitting force from the lower limbs to the upper body, improving the efficiency of power transfer, and addressing force generation issues during coordinated movements.

Yu (2023) stated that Core Stability Training emphasizes training the core muscles, which include the pelvic floor muscles, abdominal muscles, spinal extensor muscles, and diaphragm. These muscles are mainly distributed in the abdominal and lower back regions and play a significant role in body movement. Core muscles also include muscles that stabilize the core, such as the latissimus dorsi, gluteus maximus, and the three bundles of the oblique muscles. There are 29 pairs of muscles originating in the core region and 1 pair inserting into the core region, contributing to body movement and stability.

Wang (2023) explained that the "Four-Ya Structural Model" serves as the foundational mechanism for core stability, achieved by regulating the nervous system, coordinating with breathing regulation, muscle system coordination, and joint ligament strength coordination. Currently, Core Stability Training has been widely applied. Initially used primarily in rehabilitation therapy, it gradually integrated into sports, and many scholars improved athletes' specialized abilities and athletic performance through Core Stability Training. As a result, Core Stability Training has become a training method for enhancing basic motor skills and specialized skills in the human body.

Zarei (2023) emphasized that Core Stability Training is crucial for sprinters. The core muscles play a key role for sprinters in starting, accelerating, and sprinting phases. A stable core provides a solid foundation for transmitting lower limb-generated force to the upper body, improving stride frequency and length. Additionally, a strong and stable core helps maintain a straight body line, reduces energy wastage, and prevents unnecessary body sway during races, ultimately leading to better performance.

Hessam (2023) pointed out that core stability is one of the key factors influencing sprinting performance. It not only helps athletes transmit and utilize force more effectively but also ensures optimal

body posture during sprints. Therefore, specialized core stability training should be integrated into the regular training plans of sprinters to achieve optimal competitive results. Sprinting in track and field, which tests a combination of explosiveness, speed, and technique, has always been a research hotspot in sports training. In recent years, the concept and methods of Functional Training have been widely applied in many sports, and sprinting is no exception. Functional Training advocates training by simulating actual movements in competition and daily activities, improving athletes' movement efficiency and reducing the risk of injuries.

Maleki (2023) stated that Functional Training places a high emphasis on the specificity of movements, simulating key actions in sprinting during training. For example, critical movements in sprinting, such as the start, arm swing, and leg propulsion, can be practiced specifically through Functional Training. This training method often involves the coordination of various body parts, improving athletes' body coordination and balance,

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enabling them to perform technical movements more quickly and accurately, thus enhancing speed.

Jha (2022) pointed out that many exercises in Functional Training, such as multidirectional movements and reaction training, contribute to improving athletes' reaction speed. In sprinting, particularly during the starting phase, rapid bodily reactions are crucial. Through Functional Training, athletes can react more quickly, improving their success rate during starts. Sprinters face a certain risk of injury during training and competition, especially during the starting and sprinting phases. Functional Training, by simulating movements from actual competitions, enhances muscle and ligament strength and flexibility, effectively reducing the risk of common injuries such as muscle strains and joint sprains.

Abdelhalim (2022) emphasized that Functional Training often emphasizes the training of core muscle groups. Core muscles are vital for sprinters as they provide a stable foundation for the lower limbs, ensuring the consistency of movements and the output of power. Strengthening core muscle groups enhances athletes' performance and explosiveness during races.

Functional Training, through the simulation of actual competition movements, targetedly improves sprinters' technical skills, body coordination, and explosiveness. Additionally, it effectively reduces the risk of injuries. In summary, Functional Training has become a crucial component of modern sprinting training, positively impacting athletes' competitive performance.

Lower Limb Explosiveness Training

Dongaz (2023) pointed out in his research that the concept of core explosiveness originated from a deep study of the strength component in athletes' performance. In the mid to late 20th century, scientists and sports trainers realized that mere muscle size or endurance does not fully represent an individual's ability to generate maximum force in a short time. This led to the concept of "explosiveness," especially focusing on the muscle groups in the core of the body—such as the abdominal, back, and pelvic regions. Due to the critical role these core muscles play in body movement and balance, specialized research and training in their explosiveness became essential.

Salar (2023) pointed out in his study that over time, core explosiveness training gradually found application in various sports. From weightlifting, gymnastics to disciplines like taekwondo, basketball, and soccer, athletes began to undergo specialized core explosiveness training to enhance their performance in competitions. Research institutions and universities also started delving into the study of core explosiveness, publishing numerous academic articles that further demonstrated its importance in improving athletic performance, injury prevention, and enhancing overall physical function.

Yu (2023) stated in his research that in the early 21st century, with increased international sports exchanges, the concept and training methods of core explosiveness began to gain attention in China. Chinese sports trainers and coaches started going abroad for further education or invited foreign experts to conduct seminars in China. This gradually introduced the training methods of core explosiveness to China, where they were incorporated into various sports training programs. Subsequently, research

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institutions and universities in China began to conduct in-depth studies and discussions on this concept, leading to its widespread application and promotion domestically.

Wang (2023) explained in his research that core explosiveness training has been proven to be a key factor in enhancing athletic performance in various sports. The core muscle groups are responsible for body balance, turning, and power transmission. A robust core provides a stable foundation for the actions of the upper and lower limbs, allowing force to be concentrated and effectively transferred. For example, in sports like basketball, soccer, and baseball, the rotation and stability of the core are crucial for actions such as shooting, passing, and hitting. Core explosiveness training emphasizes the ability of these muscles to release maximum force in a short time, directly impacting an athlete's performance in competitions.

Zarei (2023) pointed out in his research that core explosiveness training is also regarded as a crucial strategy for reducing sports injuries. Many sports-related injuries, especially lower limb injuries, are often associated with weaknesses and imbalances in core muscles. A stable and strong core can reduce excessive stress on joints and muscles, thereby reducing the risk of sprains, strains, and collisions. Furthermore, core stability also helps maintain proper posture and body symmetry, which is crucial for long-distance running, cycling, and other endurance sports.

Hessam (2023) highlighted in his research that in technically demanding and highly coordinated sports like gymnastics, dance, and martial arts, core explosiveness training plays a vital role. Athletes in these sports need to maintain body stability during complex aerial movements and rotations. A powerful core explosiveness not only aids in the execution of these actions but also ensures stability upon landing, thereby preventing injuries. Additionally, in sports like golf, tennis, and badminton, which involve rapid body rotations and swings, a strong core ensures that power is efficiently transmitted from the legs to the upper body, enhancing striking power and accuracy.

Maleki (2023) pointed out in his research that in sports requiring rapid changes of direction, such as soccer, basketball, and tennis, the importance of core explosiveness is particularly prominent. Athletes frequently need to change direction quickly or come to a sudden stop during matches. A robust core can provide the necessary power to help athletes start, change direction, and stop rapidly, while reducing the risk of injury due to sudden movement changes.

Jha (2022) noted in his research that sprinting, as the ultimate challenge to an athlete's speed and explosiveness, places a heavy emphasis on core explosiveness. Core muscles, as the "center" of the body, play a crucial role in sprinting during the starting, accelerating, and maintaining maximum speed phases. Studies have shown that a strong core can provide a more stable body posture, allowing for more efficient transmission of power from the lower limbs. Core explosiveness training focuses on the ability of these core muscles to generate maximum force from the core area in a short period, which is critical for the starting and sprinting phases. With the widespread adoption of this training method, many top sprinters have incorporated specialized core explosiveness training into their training plans, resulting in improved performance in competitions.

In summary, core explosiveness training holds a central position in modern sports training. Whether for enhancing athletic performance or injury prevention, it has

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demonstrated its indispensable value. With further research and application, the importance of core explosiveness training will continue to be recognized and explored in the world of sports.

Synthesis. The reviewed literature underscores the quantitatively studies the training methods that are effective for short distance running results and analyzes the physical fitness profile relationship between the two, offering references for university field athletes to implement functional training and improve short- distance running results.

Before initiating speed training for short distance runners, the application of functional movement screening can effectively pinpoint improper movement patterns and compensations in foundational movements, providing a basis for accurately assessing speed potential. Catering to the speed training needs of university students, specific functional training regimes can be designed. Functional training's intervention can help correct flawed movement habits, minimize compensatory actions, and thus cultivate the correct speed movement patterns, significantly reducing injury risks during sports activities. This training system not only aids in enhancing athletes' competitive results but also effectively lowers attrition due to sports injuries, consequently extending their professional careers and providing grassroots field training teams in our country with a continuous and healthy developmental environment.

The literature emphasizes the significance of physical fitness program that lead to increased contexts of sports and physical education to improve athletes life skills(Lenzen,2023. Sports are setting that emphasizes training and performance similar to school and work, where sports skills and life skills are learned in the same way. The present study aims to incorporate this framework

Theoretical Framework

This investigation is anchored on the theory of Athletic Ability Composition Model. **Athletic Ability Composition Model** plays an indispensable role in shaping human physical movement. The athletic ability model consists of three layers: basic physical movement abilities, general athletic abilities, and specialized athletic abilities. These layers form a pyramid, progressing from bottom to top. The basic physical movement abilities form the foundation of the pyramid, providing a stable base for athletes. Compared to the general population, athletes require higher standards in stability, flexibility, and precise movement execution. General athletic abilities cover the foundational qualities needed by athletes for specific events, such as speed, power, and agility. Traditional physical training often lacks specificity in training these capabilities, while functional training more aptly meets these needs. Specialized athletic abilities directly influence an athlete's performance and are closely related to the characteristics of the sport. Functional training, with its emphasis on the quality of movement completion, is more apt for enhancing specialized physical fitness. Compared to traditional physical training, which mainly focuses on major muscle group strength, functional training stresses the power and stability of core areas, such as the spine and lumbopelvic region. This helps reduce energy wastage and enhances stability

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and flexibility. In summary, functional training's emphasis on core areas surpasses traditional training, showcasing its value in physical training.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Figure 1. illustrates the research paradigm. The study will assess the level of importance of the functional training strategies sports performance of athletes. The profile of respondents including sex, age, length of training experience. Measuring the functional motion and concept previous training experience are the input used in the pre-training assessment. Then the study focuses on the actual trainings to be conducted to student-athletes by the coaches assigned to them. And lastly, the study focuses on the level or degree of training experience and sprint performance of student-athletes. The various facets of functional trainings include core stability training, lower limb explosive strength training, multi-joint movement training, agility training, lower limb strength and endurance training, synchronous training of the trunk and upper limbs, as

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well as stretching and flexibility training. Additionally, training performance metrics, such as the 100meter and 200meter times, are considered. The research will then draw comparisons and establish among these aspects, leading to a proposed guiding framework for sprint training, all aimed at improving the short distance running performances of athletes.

Statement of the Problem

This study will determine the influence of training methods on the performance with the goal of proposing enhance training program training framework that can enhance the functional training level and sprint results of track and field athletes. Specifically, the study will seek answer to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the athletes -respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex,
 - 1.2 age,
 - 1.3 years of training as athlete?
2. What is the assessment of the athlete respondents on their level of functional motors screening before their actual training with regard to
 - 2.1 squat(deep squat)
 - 2.2 hurdle step
 - 2.3 linear lunge(in -line lunge)
 - 2.4 shoulder flexibility (shoulder mobility)
 - 2.5 active knee leg lift(active straight leg raise)
 - 2.6 torso stable push ups(trunk stability push ups)
 - 2.7 torso rotation stability (Rotary stability quadruped)
3. Is there significant difference in their level of functional motors screening when their profile is taken as a test factor?
4. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of training experience before and after the actual training experience ?
5. What is the result of the running performance of athletes in terms of the following?
 - 5.1 speed
 - 5.2 power,
 - 5.3 aerobic ,
 - 5.4 sensitivity
 - 5.5 balance
 - 5.6 explosive force
 - 5.7 tenacious tough
6. Is there significant relationship between respondents' functional motor screening and their performance as experienced ?
7. Based on the find of the study, what enhanced training program can be

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proposed?

Research Hypotheses:

The study will test the following null hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

- Ho1 There is no significant difference in their level of functional motors screening when their profile is taken as a test factor.
- Ho2 There is no significant difference in the assessment of training experience before and after the actual training experience.
- Ho3 There is no significant relationship between respondents' functional motor screening and their performance as experienced.

Significance of the Study

The present study holds the potential to provide benefits for the following beneficiaries:

Athletes. The training strategy presented in this study is designed to significantly zoom speeds of athletes and overall competitive performances. It ensures the holistic wellbeing of athletes, furnishing them with sustained support in their long-term athletic pursuits.

Sports teachers . The training methods and strategies have been finely tuned to resonate more with student needs, aiming to elevate instructional quality. The study presents a scientifically validated, rigorously structured, and holistic training methodology. This not only markedly amplifies the students' tangible training outcomes but also bolsters their course affiliation and satisfaction.

Participating schools. The present study gives a valuable opportunity, urging them to deeply reflect on and meticulously adjust their sports education and track and field training curricula. Beyond fostering a more profound academic exploration and resource allocation in sports science, athletic training, and functional trainings. It also aids the school in elevating the academic standing and reputation of institutions in the realm of track and field and sports training.

Curriculum Planners . The result could provide integration and optimization of functional training short distance running or sprinting instructions. Through the practical application of functional training, it significantly amplifies students' actual exercise outcomes, laying a solid foundation for their superior achievements in track and field.

Future Researchers. The current study paves a robust theoretical foundation for subsequent scholars, allowing for more profound exploration and extension. Moreover, the program that may be established by this research provides forthcoming researchers with a clear and valuable reference framework, guiding their future direction and strategic conceptualization.

Scope and Delimitation of Study

The student that involves assessment and analysis of the influence of functional motion screening and speed of athletes to provide valid reference for enhancing the athletic performance and training standards of the athletes .

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This research will primarily focus data to be collected for the functional motion screening and the performance of the athletes respondents. Data will be collected using survey tools and scrutinized and analyzed using mean values, percentages, Pearson's r product moment coefficient, and t-test, ANOVA test. The findings will serve as a foundation enhance future researches on functional training and development of physical fitness tests. This study will be launched for school year 2023-2024.

Definition of terms.

For clarity and understanding the following terms are defined:

Functional Training. This holistic training mode, can help the athletes to achieve the best physical condition. Functional training originated in the field of rehabilitation, and its core idea is to find and solve various problems in the movement patterns, such as the imbalance of strength, lack of coordination or lack of stability, through indepth motion screening special attention to the weaknesses of the athletes.

Physical Fitness. It refers to a state of health and well-being and, more specifically, the ability to perform aspects of sports, occupations and daily activities.

Short distance Runner. Refers to thee athlete that run in the 100,200 meters distance.

Speed. Refers to the ability of the athlete who complete certain distance for short period of time.

Core Stability Training

Core stability training focuses on strengthening deep muscles and enhancing body stability. It improves the efficiency of force transmission, essential for athletes in various sports, particularly sprinters.

Lower Limb Explosiveness Training

Core explosiveness training enhances athletic performance by focusing on the power and stability of core muscles. It reduces injury risk and improves performance in sports requiring rapid direction changes and explosive movements.

Theoretical Framework

Athletic Ability Composition Model

The Athletic Ability Composition Model comprises basic physical movement abilities, general athletic abilities, and specialized athletic abilities. Functional training addresses these layers, enhancing overall athletic performance.

Research Paradigm

The study assesses the impact of functional training on athletes' performance by evaluating functional motion screening and sprint performance before and after training interventions.

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Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the influence of functional training on athletes' performance, focusing on:

1. Athletes' profiles (sex, age, years of training).
2. Assessment of functional motion screening before training.
3. Significant differences in functional motion screening based on profiles.
4. Assessment of training experience before and after training.
5. Running performance (speed, power, aerobic endurance, sensitivity, balance, explosive force, toughness).
6. Relationship between functional motion screening and performance.
7. Proposed enhancement program based on findings.

Hypotheses

- Ho1: No significant difference in functional motion screening based on profiles.
- Ho2: No significant difference in training experience assessment before and after training.
- Ho3: No significant relationship between functional motion screening and performance.

Significance of the Study

The study benefits:

- **Athletes:** Enhancing speed and competitive performance.
- **Sports Teachers:** Improving instructional quality.
- **Participating Schools:** Adjusting sports education curricula.
- **Curriculum Planners:** Integrating functional training into sprinting instructions.
- **Future Researchers:** Providing a theoretical foundation for further studies.

Scope and Delimitation

The study focuses on assessing functional motion screening and sprint performance of athletes from a specified university, using data collected through surveys and analyzed using statistical methods.

Definition of Terms

- **Functional Training:** Exercises simulating real-life movements to enhance physical performance.
- **Physical Fitness:** State of health and well-being, ability to perform sports and daily activities.
- **Short Distance Runner:** Athletes running 100-200 meters.
- **Speed:** Ability to cover a certain distance in a short time.

Methodology

Research Design

A quasi-experimental method evaluates the athletes' functional training and running performance, comparing before and after training interventions.

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Research Locale and Respondents

Data will be collected from student athletes at a specified university, representing various training experiences.

Research Instruments

Survey checklists will record data from physical fitness exercises before and after training interventions, conducted over eight weeks.

Data Gathering Procedure

Approval will be sought from the university president, and data will be collected through online surveys, ensuring ethical considerations such as informed consent and confidentiality.

Statistical Treatment

Quantitative data will be analyzed using frequency, percentage ratio, mean, t-test, and ANOVA to determine significant differences and relationships.

References

The study references a wide range of sources, including academic articles, journals, and research papers on functional training, core stability training, and athletic performance.

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